

FABRICATION OF AL-TiB₂-B₄C COMPOSITES BY QUICK SPONTANEOUS INFILTRATION PROCESS

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1 Introduction

Over the past couple of decades, a large number of metal matrix composites (MMCs) have been of great interest as promising candidates for high-performance applications in automotive and aerospace industries [1-2]. In these materials, depending on the application and property requirement, commonly used ceramic reinforcements include SiC, B₄C, TiB₂, TiC and Al₂O₃. Boron carbide is targeted as an advanced reinforcement due to its low density, high hardness, high elastic modulus and low coefficient of thermal expansion. Titanium diboride has attractive engineering properties like exceptional hardness which is retained up to high temperature, high elastic modulus and can be rather easily wetted by aluminum compared with B₄C. The combination of both boron carbide and titanium diboride reinforced aluminum matrix results in enhanced properties of the composites than when either of the reinforcement is used. There has already been a considerable amount of research to fabricate the metal matrix composites reinforced with TiC and TiB₂. However, due to the poor wettability between the ceramics and metal, reports on the B₄C/TiB₂/Al composites are rare.

To disperse those kinds of reinforcement uniformly in the aluminum matrix, several processing techniques, such as stir-casting, powder metallurgy and melt infiltration [3-6], were developed. However, each fabrication technique has its own advantages and limitations. Some of the problems encountered are: residual microporosity, uneven distribution of reinforcement, control of the matrix-reinforcement interface, scaling up of the process for industrial utilization and processing cost and so on.

Among the processing techniques, melt infiltration is a traditional processing technique to produce MMCs

with high volume fraction of reinforcements. Several extra approaches such as applying pressure to the melt, modifying the surface of ceramics and incorporating an activator element like titanium [3, 4, 7] have been established depending on modifying the ceramic reinforcement or the matrix to improve the infiltration. In all these works, more than an hour of processing time should be necessary no matter what method they used at disposal to circumvent the wettability problem. In addition, those infiltration techniques had very high demands for its process atmosphere, either vacuum or inert atmosphere. A long processing time and severe atmospheric condition certainly would increase the cost inevitably and would not be beneficial on commercial grounds.

In the present investigation, the feasibility of a novel quick spontaneous infiltration process (QSI) is presented that enables to produce aluminum matrix composites containing high volume fraction of B₄C and/or TiB₂ with sound microstructure. The core innovation of the process is that it combines a simple pressureless infiltration in air with a combustion reaction in molten aluminum by the aid of dopant which accelerates the combustion reaction and wave propagation. This realizes quick infiltration within a few minutes and thus the process is promising for scale-up production of composites in a simple and economical way.

2 Experimental

The following powders were used as starting reagents: Ti (99.5%, ~50 μm), Al (99.5%, ~30 μm), B₄C (99.5%, ~16 μm), C(graphite, 99.9%, ~10 μm), TiO₂(99.5%, ~1.5 μm), B₂O₃ (99.5%, ~260 μm), and CuO (99.95%, ~10 μm) powders.

The reagent powders were mixed at a proper mole ratio for an hour and then compacted at room

temperature into a cylindrical shape to make a pellet (h=28 mm, d=35 mm, 55-60% of the theoretical density). The pellet was dried in a vacuum oven at 200 °C for 2 hours to eliminate the moisture.

In the present work, four kinds of MMCs having different reinforcements were produced by QSI process. Each scheme of composition in the initial powder mixtures are shown in Table 1 to 3.

Table 1. Compositions of Al-Ti-B₄C powder mixtures.

No	Composition (mole)		remarks
	Ti	B ₄ C	
SA	3	1	Small amount of CuO and excess Al were added
SB	3	4	

Table 2. Compositions of Al-B₂O₃-C powder mixtures.

No	Composition (mole)			remarks
	Al	B ₂ O ₃	C	
SC	4	2	1	Small amount of CuO and excess Al were added

Table 3. Compositions of Al-TiO₂-B₂O₃ powder mixtures.

No	Composition (mole)			remarks
	Al	TiO ₂	B ₂ O ₃	
SD	10	3	3	Small amount of CuO and excess Al were added

Fig. 1 provides a schematic representation of the QSI process. The pellet was placed inside a graphite tube mold and the mold was put into an aluminum melt that was kept at 1073~1273 K. The melt temperature differs with the type of initial powder mixtures shown in Table 1 to 3. Before ignition the top surface of the pellet was exposed to air in order to remove pellet's internal gas and moisture easily, which are inevitably absorbed in the surface of powders. Immediately after the onset of ignition, with the evidence of dazzling light that originated from the reaction of the powder mixtures, the mold was dipped into the aluminum melt so as to infiltrate aluminum melt into the pellet. Finally, the mold was

taken out from the melt, and cooled down in air. The whole process was completed in 4 minutes in air.

Fig. 1 Schematic diagram showing the quick spontaneous infiltration process.

For the microstructural analysis, samples were sectioned and prepared using standard polishing procedures with a final polishing by a 0.05µm colloidal silica suspension. Microstructures were investigated by means of an optical microscope (OM) and a scanning electron microscope (SEM) equipped with an energy-dispersive spectrometer (EDS). X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis with Cu K α radiation was also carried out to identify the phases.

The elastic properties and CTE of the samples were measured using resonant ultrasound spectroscopy and a dilatometer system, respectively.

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Macrostructures

Fig. 2 shows the typical view of the cross section of the pellet after infiltration. Under the optimum processing parameter such as melt temperature, amount of CuO and excess aluminum in the powder mixtures, the composites retained their initial shape of the pellet well and were free of cracks (Fig. 2b); the aluminum melt was infiltrated up to the top surface of the pellet. However, if the processing parameters were not proper, there remained pores, cracks and uninfiltreated parts in the pellet (Fig. 2a).

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It was confirmed that the soundness of MMCs by QSI process strongly depends on such processing parameters. The detailed results will be reported in a future study.

Fig. 2 A cross section of the pellet composites fabricated by QSI using the powder mixtures of Al-Ti-B₄C (SB) in the different processing parameters. (a) composites having cracks and pores (b) sound composites having free of cracks and pores

3.2 Microstructures

The microstructures of the composites shown in Figs. 3-6 exhibited quasi-continuous 3D network structures composed of infiltrated aluminum and reinforcing particles surrounded by a large amount of aggregates of the reaction products throughout the specimens.

Fig. 3 shows the microstructures of the composites using the initial powder mixture of SA samples. The microstructures are composed of aggregates of TiC+TiB₂ with aluminum throughout the whole pellet. The size of both particles is very fine less than 1μm. In addition, no trace of B₄C is observed. In an Al-Ti-B₄C system with a mole ratio of Ti/B₄C=3, the following reactions are expected to occur;

Thus, during the process, initial B₄C particles reacted with Ti particles to form TiB₂ and TiC completely.

Fig.3 Microstructures of the composites fabricated by QSI using the powder mixtures of Al-Ti-B₄C (SA) with (a) low magnification and (b) high magnification image.

The microstructures of the composites (SB sample) shown in Fig. 4 exhibited quasi-continuous 3D network structures composed of infiltrated aluminum and B₄C particles surrounded by a large amount of aggregates of the reaction products throughout the samples.

It was confirmed by SEM/EDS and XRD analysis that the main reaction products are TiB₂ and Al₃BC. In addition, small amount of Al₃Ti were also observed in the microstructure. The aggregates of the reaction products such as TiB₂, Al₃BC, and Al₃Ti, were confirmed by TEM to have very fine sizes (less than 0.5 μm in size) and to be disconnected from each other.

Fig.4 Microstructures of the composites fabricated by QSI using the powder mixtures of Al-Ti-B₄C (SB) with (a) low magnification and (b) high magnification image.

In an Al-Ti-B₄C system with a mole ratio of Ti/B₄C=0.75, the reactions are rather complicated due to non-stoichiometric composition ratio of Ti/B₄C and following reactions are expected to occur;

In the microstructures, no trace of TiC is observed and a large amount of Al₃BC is formed instead. In addition, additional phase such as Al₃Ti is present in the microstructures. It means that an incomplete reaction occurred, with fewer B₄C particles decomposed, according to the equation (4).

To determine the reaction occurred in the pellet, the volume fractions of the initial powder mixtures and final microstructures in the reacted pellet were compared. The density of each phase used in the calculation is summarized in Table 4.

Table 4. Density of the particles.

phase	Al	B ₄ C	TiB ₂	Al ₃ BC	Al ₃ Ti
Density (g/cm ³)	2.7	2.52	4.52	2.85	3.37

Ignoring the content of CuO and considering the content of the aluminum melt that was infiltrated, the volume fraction of B₄C (16 μm in size) in the initial pellet is calculated to be 25.7%. In addition, the volume fraction of B₄C in the composites was measured to be 18.3%, with an average particle size of 7.7 μm by the image analysis.

The calculated volume fraction of each phase according to equations (3) and (4) is summarized in Table 5.

Table 5. Calculated volume fraction of each phase according to equation (3) and (4). (unit: vol.%)

reaction	B ₄ C	TiB ₂	Al ₃ BC	Al ₃ Ti
(3)	13.4	14.3	22.5	-
(4)	16.3	10.4	16.4	8.6

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Comparing the measured and calculated value of B₄C volume fraction in the pellet, incomplete reaction occurred according to equation (4) in the SB sample.

Fig. 5 shows the microstructures of the composites using the initial powder mixture of SC samples. The microstructures are composed of B₄C particles and aggregates of Al₂O₃ particles with aluminum throughout the whole pellet. The size of Al₂O₃ particles is very fine and closely connected each other.

In an Al-B₂O₃-C system, the following reactions are expected to occur;

Fig.5 Microstructures of the composites fabricated by QSI using the powder mixtures of Al-B₂O₃-C (SC) with (a) low magnification and (b) high magnification image.

Thus, during the process, complete reaction occurred in the pellet to form Al₂O₃ and B₄C in the microstructures.

Fig. 6 shows the microstructures of the composites using the initial powder mixture of SD samples. The microstructures are composed of aggregates of TiB₂ and aggregates of Al₂O₃ particles with aluminum throughout the whole pellet. The size of Al₂O₃ particles is very fine and closely connected each other. The size of TiB₂ particles is also very fine less than 1μm, however, the particles are disconnected each other.

Fig.6 Microstructures of the composites fabricated by QSI using the powder mixtures of Al-TiO₂-B₂O₃ (SD) with (a) low magnification and (b) high magnification image.

In an Al-TiO₂-B₂O₃ system, the following reactions are expected to occur;

Thus, during the process, complete reaction occurred in the pellet to form Al₂O₃ and TiB₂ in the microstructures.

3.3 Infiltration

To clarify the quick infiltration through the process, the combustion temperature was monitored using a c-type thermocouple embedded in the pellet, along with a data acquisition system for SB samples. In addition, several identical pellets were prepared to obtain mass gain during the process. The mass gain was checked every 5 seconds before and after the onset of ignition during the process without dipping the mold into the melt. We confirmed that melt infiltration occurred for 15~20 seconds after the ignition. The detailed results are described elsewhere [8].

The following pressures are known to act during the infiltration process,

$$P = P_A + P_C - \rho gl = \Delta P - \rho gl \quad (7)$$

$$P_C = \frac{2\gamma_{lv} \cos \theta}{r_c} \quad (8)$$

$$r_c = \frac{dV_f}{3\lambda(1-V_f)} \quad (9)$$

where P_A is the atmospheric pressure difference between the inside and the outside of the pellet, P_C is the capillary pressure, ρ is the liquid density, g is gravitational acceleration, l is the infiltration length, γ_{lv} is the surface tension, θ is the contact angle, r_c is the capillary radius, d is particle size, and λ is the geometric factor determined by the capillary and particle geometries [9-11].

Using equations (7), (8), (9) and Washburn relationship [11], the infiltration time-length relationship was derived as follows.

$$t = \left(\frac{8\eta}{r_c^2}\right)\left(\frac{1}{\rho g}\right)\left[\left(\frac{\Delta P}{\rho g}\right)\ln\left(\frac{1}{1 - \left(\frac{\rho g}{\Delta P}\right)l}\right) - l\right] \quad (10)$$

where η is the viscosity of liquid aluminum.

In the pressure infiltration, the gravitational pressure term is small enough to be ignored, whereas it should be considered in the pressureless infiltration, especially when the reaction is performed in air. If ΔP >> ρgl, then Equation (10) becomes identical to well-known Equation (11) in the form of l² ∝ t [4,11].

$$t = \frac{4\eta}{r_c^2 \cdot \Delta P} l^2 \quad (11)$$

Using Equation (10), the infiltration time-length relationship for the Al-B₄C system can be calculated. The calculated results show that the infiltration is completed within a very short time of 2 ~ 18 seconds, which matches well with the results of mass gain in the present work. The detailed results are described elsewhere [8].

3.4 Role of CuO

The QSI process is the combination of a simple pressureless infiltration in air with a combustion reaction in molten aluminum. Thus, the occurrence of combustion reaction and wave propagation is one of the key factors to realize the process.

The adiabatic temperature (T_{ad}) can be used as a general indication of the temperature at the combustion front. It has been empirically suggested that combustion reactions will not become self-sustaining unless T_{ad} > 1800K [12]. According to the enthalpy change between the reactants and the products, T_{ad} of the each materials system can be calculated.

Fig. 7 shows the change of T_{ad} with the addition of excess Al content for Al-3Ti-B₄C system (SA sample) without CuO. The calculated result shows that theoretical adiabatic temperature exceeds 1800K; it means that the combustion reaction occurs and combustion wave can be propagated over the pellet. However, in the actual process, a mere elemental powder mixture could not induce the complete reaction in the pellet even though it ignited.

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Fig.7 Change of T_{ad} with the addition of excess Al content for Al-3Ti-B₄C system (SA sample) without CuO.

It is due to the occurrence of heat loss during the process. During the process, extensive heat can be generated in the powder mixtures once it is ignited. However, the heat can be consumed to increase the melt temperature and infiltrated aluminum melt (heat loss to the surroundings), as well as to sustain further combustion reactions. Due to this reason, incomplete reaction occurred for CuO-free pellets. Fig. 8 compares the measured temperature profile with time during the process for SA samples with and without CuO addition.

Fig.8 Time-temperature profile for Al-3Ti-B₄C system (SA sample) with and without CuO during the process.

In the CuO-free pellet, the peak temperature is much below the T_{ad} even though it ignited. Addition of CuO sharply increased the peak temperature of the Al-3Ti-B₄C system.

It has been verified that a thermal explosion that generated a large quantity of exothermic heat can be observed when adding CuO to molten aluminum [13] as follows;

Fig. 9 shows the change of T_{ad} with the addition of excess Al content for Al-CuO system. Thus, it is proposed that CuO addition plays a role in releasing great amounts of additional heat and thereby self-sustaining the combustion reaction by compensating for the heat loss to the surroundings during the process.

Fig.9 Change of T_{ad} with the addition of excess Al content for Al-CuO.

3.5 Properties

The properties of sound SB samples (Fig 2 b) were measured. The density of composites was found to be 2.940g/cm³; the microstructures of the composites were sound, with few pores; the calculated porosity was less than 1.0%. The composites exhibited a high hardness value of 3.03 GPa and a high elastic modulus of 158.9 GPa (shear modulus 63.7 GPa, bulk modulus 104.7 GPa) with a low CTE of 9.4 ppm/K; these values show properties equivalent to those obtained from aluminum matrix

composites containing 50-60 vol.% of SiC particles [14].

4 Summary

Aluminum matrix composites having TiB₂ and/or B₄C particles were produced by quick spontaneous infiltration process in a few minutes in air from the different initial powder mixtures. The soundness of MMCs by the process depended on processing parameters and the microstructures of the composites exhibited quasi-continuous 3D network structures composed of infiltrated aluminum and reinforcing particles surrounded by a large amount of aggregates of the reaction products. The Al-B₄C-TiB₂ composites exhibited excellent mechanical properties: 3GPa for Vickers hardness, 159GPa for elastic modulus and 9.4ppm/K for coefficient of thermal expansion.

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